

PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS ON MATHEMATICS LEARNING

A Seminar Paper
Presented to the
Faculty of the Graduate School
Cagayan State University-Andrews Campus
Tuguegarao City

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Science in Teaching
Major in Mathematics

by
KRISTOFFER PAULO LORETCHA RAMIREZ
March 2016

ABSTRACT

Title: PERCEPTIONS OF STUDENTS ON MATHEMATICS LEARNING

Researcher: KRISTOFFER PAULO LORETCH RAMIREZ

Degree: MASTER OF SCIENCE IN TEACHING – MATHEMATICS

Institution: CAGAYAN STATE UNIVERSITY – ANDREWS CAMPUS, TUGUEGARAO CITY

Adviser: DR. LETICIA A. DUMLAO

This study was conducted to determine how College of Human Kinetics (CHK) students perceived Mathematics learning. Using survey questionnaire to 171 freshmen students, results were then determined, tabulated and analyzed. It was observed that there is an almost equal ratio of males to females, having almost 43% of male population.

Respondents perceived most of the mathematics subject as moderate with Advance algebra and trigonometry and college algebra perceived as difficult. It could also be further observed that there is a perceived increasing difficulty of Mathematics subjects as one goes up from each year level. Moreover, students have all agreed that mathematics is a subject of calculable, involves in depth thinking and is useful in which the first one is strongly agreed upon. There is a moderate feeling, which is between positive and negative attitude, connected towards mathematics subject in terms of interest, preference for understanding, confidence and confidence. It could also be noted

that students almost spend a third to half of their hours studying or doing Mathematics homework.

When meeting difficulties in Mathematics learning, students sometimes take positive steps in understanding such as consulting the teacher, asking classmates or experts and searching additional references such as books. Giving up is not an option to students. When meeting difficulties in solving different Mathematics problems, students sometimes do any possible options on hand to solve the latter; from insisting on doing it themselves, consulting other people to copying others work.

In summary, students rated Mathematics as moderate or difficult with an observable increasing trend of difficulty as each student proceeds to another level; students agreed that Mathematics is a subject of calculable, involves thinking and useful, with the first conception strongly agreed by the students; students associate Mathematics with a neutral feeling as regard to interest, preference for understanding, confidence and competence; students spend a considerable time studying or doing homework in Mathematics; students sometimes take positive actions when facing difficulties in Mathematics learning; and students sometimes try any available options, even if considered as positive or negative, when meeting difficulties in solving Mathematics problems.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study:

Many factors of effective learning transfer are being studied by educators to maximize learning. These, when understood, will give access on how students learn and what educators could do to improve such. Factors such as belief, teaching methodologies, conception, attitude, motivation, social and learning styles are deemed significant to be studied as to give quality learning.

One factor that is considerably important to study is about students' perception towards educational processes because evidences have shown that how they understand those processes impacts their educational experiences. Students, who take responsibility for their learning, generally achieve more (Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Ryan & Grolnick, 1986); whereas, those who locate control or apportion responsibility elsewhere (Rotter, 1982) or who lack confidence to achieve (Bandura, 1989; Pajares, 1996) tend to achieve less.

Student's perception about Mathematics learning is one of the main concerns of Mathematics educators at present. Mathematics is at the heart of many successful careers and successful lives for societal development, particularly in the extraordinary and accelerating change circumstances.

However, beyond this vital importance, most people, in general and students in particular, dislike mathematics.

The review of school-based educational research has revealed that the majority of secondary school students find mathematics as the most difficult, abstract, tedious, deadly, and boring subject (Ernest, 1996; Wong, Lam & Wong, 2001; Nardi & Steward, 2003; and Kirsti, Grevholm & Lepik, 2005).

These negative conceptions of mathematics have a major impact on students' achievement, enrollment in higher education and their future career decisions (Sam, 1999). It is so because their views or beliefs affect how they behave in learning situations, which in turn, affect the way they learn mathematics (Frank, 1988; Spangler, 1992).

Further, attitudes and dispositions permeates the teaching and learning mathematics. What students believe about mathematics influences what they are willing to say publicly, what questions they are likely to pose, what risk they are willing to take, and what connections they are to make outside the classroom.

Along these studies, the researcher decided to determine how students view mathematics learning: the perceived difficulty in different Mathematics subjects, their beliefs or conception, their attitude towards mathematics and their learning habits.

Hence, this study.

Statement of the Problem:

This study was conducted to determine how College of Human Kinetics (CHK) students view Mathematics learning.

Thus, the following problems were sought to be answered:

1. How do CHK students perceive the difficulty of mathematics subjects?
2. What is the conception of CHK students on Mathematics learning in terms of its:
 - a. Nature as calculable
 - b. Involvement to thinking
 - c. Usability?
3. What is the attitudinal level of CHK students towards Mathematics learning with regard to:
 - a. Interest
 - b. Preference for understanding
 - c. Confidence
 - d. Competence?
4. What are the coping mechanisms of CHK students in Mathematics learning with regards to:
 - a. Number of hours spent in studying mathematics.
 - b. Coping mechanisms of students when encountering difficulties in mathematics
 - c. Coping mechanisms of students when encountering problems in solving mathematics problems?

Significance of the Study:

This study hopes to be beneficial to the following stakeholders:

From the results of the study, the students involved would be able to determine their general characteristics and perception when it comes to mathematics learning thus, would help them realize how these have affected their mathematics performance.

The results will also be useful to the College in determining the possible programs that may improve mathematics learning. Further, the results can be used to guide the development of a classroom environment conducive to growth into positive attitudes and in addressing misconception and counterproductive skills.

This may also be beneficial to the university as a pre-survey research in conducting university wide researches that may would give information on how students perceived Mathematics education and consequently conduct programs and appropriate funds to each to improve mathematics learning.

Lastly, this study could serve as an instrument to discuss to the whole region the existing views of college students in mathematics and how each of the communal could help in determining solutions to further alleviate mathematics education in the society.

These could be the contributions of the study in the field of research along the essentials of studying the views of students towards mathematics learning.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study:

This study was limited in describing the views of CHK students towards mathematics learning: particularly on their perceived difficulty in the different

Mathematics subjects they have taken in, from high school to present; extent in which they agree to the general conceptions of students towards mathematics; attitudinal level focusing on interest, preference for understanding, confidence and competence; and learning habits towards Mathematics learning.

This study is limited to students' views for the academic second semester year 2015 – 2016. This study was then delimited to the first year students of CHK students. This study included 171 first year CHK students who are enrolled in the mathematics course being offered in the first year.

Survey questionnaire was the only tool to gather the data of the respondents involving their profile and their views to mathematics learning. Additional statements, as inculcated in the questionnaire, if added by the respondent, were also gathered and analyzed to support the answered checklist of each view.

Informal interviews and direct observation were also conducted to random respondents to further understand and analyze the accumulated data gathered.

This study was then conducted from December to March 2016.

Definition of Terms:

Student's **perceptions on mathematics learning** refers to the general view of the students towards their educational experiences in mathematics course. This includes conception, attitude, perceived difficulty or coping mechanisms.

The **level of difficulty** of mathematics subject refers to the general perception of students on how difficult the mathematics subject considering their whole experience for such.

Student's **conception** towards mathematics learning refers to their belief or on how student's perceived or regarded mathematics as a course.

Student's **attitude** may refer to the feelings that is being reflected in their behavior towards mathematics which includes their interest, preference towards understanding different math problems, confidence and competence in solving mathematics dilemmas.

Learning habits of students refers to respondents preferred action when he encounter difficulty in learning or in solving problems in mathematics.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE:

This study aims to assess different views of students towards mathematics learning by synthesizing relevant literature and emerging findings related to student success, broadly defined.

Students Views towards Mathematics

Generally, students' views of mathematics are developed based on their school learning experiences (Schoenfeld, 1989; Ernest, 1996) and how the public image of mathematics is portrayed in the society (Sam, 1999).

Some of the other viewpoints students hold about mathematics include: mathematics problems have one and only one answer and they can be solved in a particular way; mathematics is a solitary activity, done by individuals in isolation; mathematics requires good memory and is only for clever ones.

Perceived Difficulty of Mathematics Subjects

Most students perceived Mathematics as a difficult subject to deal with. Wong, Lam and Wong (2001) revealed that most of the topics in Mathematics are perceived to be difficult with an observable trend that as those topics require abstraction, level of difficulty increases.

Reasons why these have been the perception of the students have been continuously studied by educators to seek answers regarding the existing view. As being presented by Bhattacharya (2014), Mathematics is difficult to relate to since it is dealing with something entirely new whose practical implications in daily life are hard to

imagine; the farther anything moves from reality, the more difficult it becomes to comprehend. He also indicate the objectivity of Mathematics as one factor why it is considered as difficult. The nature of Mathematics to have a definite answer adds burden to learning mathematics.

Research studies have also showed that poor teaching is a limiting factor in which students find Mathematics difficult. If mathematics is taught badly; wherein students are committed to rote learning or adhered to specific methodology, they will lose the core field of good understanding Mathematics, which are creativity and imagination.

Conception on Mathematics Learning

Thompson (1992) describes conceptions as “conscious or subconscious beliefs, concepts, meanings, rules, mental images, and preferences” (p. 132). Conception towards mathematics may then be referred to beliefs, associated concepts, meanings, predetermined rules, mental images formed and learning preferences towards mathematics.

Different conception in mathematics have emerge throughout the years. These different conceptions of mathematics, as being argued by Dossey (1992), influence the ways in which society views mathematics. This can influence the teaching of mathematics and communicates subtle messages to children about the nature of mathematics that “affect the way they grow to view mathematics and its role in their world” (p. 42).

Similarly, Presmeg (2002) has argued that beliefs about the nature of mathematics either enable or constrain “the bridging process between everyday practices and school mathematics” (p. 295)

Examples of such conceptions were revealed by Sam and Ernest (2008) in which mathematics is identified with numbers and equations, rules and procedures, pattern and structures. Mathematics is also viewed as a practical tool, a model, a language, a science or a discipline of study.

Loveridge (2007) also determined in their study that majority of students mentioned “number” as the nature of Mathematics. This is consistent with Grootenboer’s (2003) and Fuson et al. (2005) findings that children’s reflected views of mathematics tended to revolve around number concepts and arithmetic.

The study also revealed that only few students perceived usefulness of mathematics to “here and now” than referred to the usefulness of mathematics for their futures. Future uses included later schooling, “getting a good education”, and getting a job.

This is in parallel to Whittin (2007) suggesting only few students indicate that math is useful at present, most them relate usefulness in future employment.

Finally, Sam and Ernest (2007) disclosed that people generally have beliefs that mathematics is difficult but possible to achieve success in, examples mathematics is 'like Mt. Everest, difficult to climb but not impossible' [R522].

In higher education, students’ learning is more influenced by their perceptions of the educational environment than by the actual educational practices (Entwistle, 1991).

And sadly, most of the students view mathematics in negative way. Some people, as in the results of Sam and Ernest (2007) study, view mathematics as boring, difficult and find hard to cope with, incomprehensible, misleading or confusing. Further, Whittin (2007) reveals that in general, students view mathematics learning as solitary endeavor studied by individuals alone due to its nature of “working in textbook” or “to calculate” (Skoverkert, 2003)

Different dichotomies have been used to highlight the contrasting ways in which mathematics is viewed. For example, Dossey (1992) has distinguished between external conceptions of mathematics, held by those who believe that mathematics is a fixed body of knowledge that is presented to students, and internal conceptions that view mathematics as personally constructed, internal knowledge.

Begg (1994, 2005) has contrasted mathematical content (knowledge and procedures) with mathematical processes (reasoning, problem solving, communicating, and making connections). Winter (2001) has written about a tension between a mechanistic view of mathematics (as in the development of skills and knowledge) and mathematics as a means towards fostering citizenship and responsibility within society (as in the development of personal, spiritual, moral, social, and cultural dimensions).

Pehkonen and Törner (1998) conclude that mathematical beliefs as a regulating system has a prognostic character. In their words, mathematical beliefs form a frame for an individual’s knowledge structure broadly influences the mathematics performance of the individual.

Attitude towards Mathematics Learning

In the study conducted by Johansson & Sumpter, (2010), they have described that Mathematics is connected to positive feeling. Further, they have concluded that Mathematics as a subject is an individual activity - to sit down and work in the textbook. It seems, based on their results, that the motivation is both positive intrinsic (because it is fun and they want to learn) and negative extrinsic (because the teacher says so and you need to finish the textbook).

However, Whittin (2007) revealed a belief that math is silent and solitary endeavor. Her study reveals that children view mathematics class as a period of teacher – student interaction in which teachers pose problems and evaluate the answers. She also reveals that speed is the universal measure of mathematics success.

Finally, Sam and Ernest (2008) revealed that the three most common expressions used in Mathematics are 'mathematics is difficult'; 'mathematics is boring' or 'mathematics is interesting or rewarding'. Metaphors which show positive images such as 'mathematics is like playing with my children, never tiresome' [R526] or negative images such as 'like eating nails -hard and painful' [RIII] are also commonly expressed.

Further, over 44% of the entries indicate some kind of attitude, feeling or emotion. They range from positive attitudes such as 'mathematics is fun and exciting' [RI70] to negative attitudes such as 'mathematics is dull, boring complex' [RI82]. Others emphasize the importance of mathematics such as 'mathematics is important for everything' [RI75] while yet others see mathematics as 'irrelevant' [R053] and 'a lot of things which I will never use' [R059]

Learning Habits towards Mathematics.

Whittin (2007) reveals that when students are having troubles in math, students depend on teachers for proper direction. Some students skip the problem for proper time management.

Sam and Ernest (2008) described Mathematics as process of 'hard work' [R034], or effortful endeavour as 'something required concentration-satisfy when right' [R090]; a repetitive process, example, Math is 'repetitive, structures and logical' [R105].

The aforesaid research results revealed that researchers and educators continue to determine different student views of mathematics learning and how it could affect such process. Significant issues with regards to this views were emphasized as to determine the links that exist between views and learnings.

In this chapter, the researcher offered what he deemed significant for the interpretation of the results herein. It is only hope that parallelism and contradiction in the abovementioned results would be accepted and considered for the researcher have pushed this study to its frontiers.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes how this study was conducted. It presents the methods of research that were used, the respondents of the study, sampling procedure, the data gathering tools, and the procedures employed for gathering the data needed to answer the research problems.

It must be noted that this is a parallel study to the research conducted by Wong, Lam and Wong (2001) entitled “Students’ view of Mathematics Learning: A Cross Sectional Survey in Hong Kong”.

As such, this research have almost followed the design presented by the study presented above to determine consistency of the results presented across the Asian regions.

Research Methods

This research utilizes descriptive survey design. It aimed to provide quantitative and qualitative description on different views of mathematics learning based on the weighted mean of the respondents for each statement presented.

Locale and Respondents of the Study

The population frame of the study covered 171 first year college students of College of Human Kinetics of Cagayan State University - Carig Campus - Tuguegarao City for the academic year 2015 – 2016.

Sampling Procedure

This study used Slovin's formula with 5% marginal error to determine the total number of respondents involving first year students of the College of Human Kinetics enrolled in College Algebra course.

From the 300 population frame of the respondents, 171 students were randomly chose using systematic random sampling technique. The study then comprised 74 males and 97 females.

Research Instrument

Survey questionnaire using five point rating scale and checklist was the main instrument used in determining the responses of the respondents with regards to their views of mathematics learning.

The survey questionnaire with five point rating scale was used in determining the perceived difficulty of different math subjects they have taken in. Five point rating scale was used in analyzing their perceived conceptions or beliefs towards mathematics learning. Five point Likert scale is likewise used in determining the degree of agreement to determine their attitudes towards math. A checklist was used in determining respondent's learning habits towards mathematics.

Open ended questions were also provided in the survey questionnaire to allow respondents to identify other existing views that have not been included in the study. The statements used in the study were lifted from the research conducted by Wong, Lam,

Wong (2001) with little modification to fit to the social and demographical situations of Filipino people.

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter was personally delivered to the dean of the College of Human Kinetics for the permission to conduct the study. After the request of permission was favorably granted, the survey questionnaires were floated. After the completion, the questionnaires were immediately retrieved.

Analysis of Data

The data gathered from the respondents were classified, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted based on the profile of the respondents.

5 point rating scale was used in interpreting the perceived difficulty of different math subjects the respondents have taken in.

INTERVAL	DESCRIPTION AND INTERPRETATION
4.21 – 5.00	Very Difficult
3.41 – 4.20	Difficult
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Easy
1.00 – 1.80	Very Easy

5 point rating scale was used in determining the degree of agreement on the identified conception of Mathematics.

INTERVAL	DESCRIPTION AND INTERPRETATION
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
3.41 – 4.20	Agree
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree

5 point rating scale is likewise use in determining the attitudinal scale of the respondents towards mathematics.

INTERVAL	INTERPRETATION
4.21 – 5.00	Very Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Neutral
1.81 – 2.60	Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Very Negative

4 point rating scale was used in the checklist of learning habits of students towards mathematics.

INTERVAL	DESCRIPTION AND INTERPRETATION
3.25 – 4.00	Always
2.50 – 3.25	Sometimes
1.75 – 2.50	Seldom
1.00 – 1.75	Never

CAGAYAN STATE UNIVERSITY

GRADUATE SCHOOL

20

Statistical Treatment of Data

Mean and frequency counts were used in determining and analyzing student's profile. Weighted mean is used in analyzing student's perceived difficulty, conception, attitude, and learning habits. Sum and percentages were used in determining the ratio of hours spend in mathematics as compared to other subjects.

CHAPTER IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the data gathered based on the study conducted through the use of scientific and valid statistical analysis and presentation of information.

It must be noted that the researcher did not only limit the study in answering the given questions but rather included some responses on the open ended questions presented in the questionnaire to satisfy the queries that may arise regarding the students' view towards Mathematics learning.

Profile of the Respondents:

The table presents the distribution of the respondents according to sex. It can be gleaned that there is an almost equal number of males and females in the college in which males comprises 43.3% of the whole population. This implies that Bachelor of Physical education course is not only attractive for females but also for males. This data may be attributed to the fact that the said course has sports related field which greatly attracted sports minded male athletes.

Table 1: Frequency Table of the Respondents in terms of sex.

	Frequency	Percent
Male	74	43.3%
Female	97	56.7%
Total	171	100.0%

This result may therefore change the assertion of Esplanada (2009) stating that there is an endangerment of males in the field of teaching.

Perception of Students on Difficulty of Mathematics Subject:

The table reveals the perceived difficulty of CHK students in the different Mathematics subjects they have taken in. It can be seen in the table that Advance Algebra and Trigonometry and College Algebra are perceived difficult.

These can be verified through the responses given by the students that math is difficult because “there’s a lot of numbers and letters that you need to understand” [r114] and many problems [r129] formulas [r99] and solutions [r110] to understand. And sometimes I forget them [r7]”; “It’s like a tornado that is so very hard to understand” [r58]; “there is a problem that we cannot solve within that topic” [r112]; “Math is very complicated [r187] and not easy to understand unless you are a mathematician [r116]”.

However, although some students find Mathematics as difficult, “that sometimes it cracks my brain [r184], makes my nose bleed, and makes me crazy” and actually “I hate math” [r95] lines, some students find that “it’s fun [r28] and it makes you happy.” Ultimately, students are trying to love it for them to understand [r93]”.

Others, as revealed in the table, perceived Mathematics as moderate or easy. Which is a good indication in which students actually find it easy to understand Mathematics. This can be verified through the responses given by the respondents. These statements confirm that Mathematics is not so difficult if “I am getting serious to the subject” [r141] and it depends on the topic [r195]” and “if you listen to the teacher while he is teaching” [r115] although confusing if the problems are all seemed the same but requires different solutions” [r4]. Some students even pointed out that level of difficulty

depends on the teacher stating that “Sometimes I can understand it if the teacher explained step by step carefully [r194]: it depends on how the teacher teach the student [r185].

Finally, one students compared it to love stating that “It’s like love, sometimes you are struggling but at the end, it will turned out to be easy” [r123].

It can be further observed that there is an increasing trend of difficulty in the high school and college Mathematics subjects from easy to difficult. This implies that learners find Mathematics as becoming difficult to understand. This trend could be attributed to the fact of the increasing abstraction of Mathematics subjects they are enrolling with

Table 2: Perception of students on the difficulty of Mathematics subjects

Subject	Mean	Descriptive Value
Elementary Algebra	2.22	Easy
Intermediate Algebra	2.74	Moderately Difficult
Geometry	3.09	Moderately Difficulty
Advance Algebra and Trigonometry	3.49	Difficult
Basic Math	2.80	Moderately Difficulty
College Algebra	3.56	Difficult
Weighted Mean	2.98	Moderately Difficult

These results could be patterned with the study conducted by Wong, Lam, Wong (2001) revealing that as students moved up the grade levels, they found mathematics more and more difficult.

Conception of Students towards Mathematics Learning

It can be seen in the table presented that students perceived Mathematics as calculable, involves thinking and useful.

It can be observed that students strongly agreed to the statement that Mathematics involves addition, subtraction, multiplication or division which signifies that they perceived Mathematics as highly calculable. Further, it can also be observed that students also agreed strongly on the statements that this subject requires computation and involves solving problems. This implies that students have been oriented that Mathematics subject is centered on calculations.

It can also be observed that the respondents agreed on the statements that Mathematics allows students to practice their critical thinking skills and that understanding the concept is the more important than simply memorizing the formula.

This signifies that students also believe that learning mathematics requires in depth thinking to develop knowledge and skills necessary for life. This can be reflected on the response of one respondent stating that Mathematics “helps in developing knowledge [r116] and problem solving skills that could be used in real life situations” [r17].

It’s surprising to note however that students actually perceived Mathematics as useful in their daily lives and their future endeavors even though their course does not need a high competence on Mathematics. These can be supported by the responses of the respondents that “we can use Mathematics in all things, present in any kind of situation [r28] and it is of a great help to humans” [r33] because “we use math in our daily routines [r201] and lives such as buying” [r26].

Some students even consider the usability of learning Mathematics as “we will need math to be successful in our educational career [r93]: for our future [r30], future jobs [r5] like computing grades [r106] and other endeavors like business” [r7].

Table 3a: Conception of students on Mathematics learning in terms of its nature as calculable.

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Value
Mathematics involves adding, subtracting, multiplying and dividing numbers	4.45	Strongly agree
Mathematics is a subject that requires computation.	4.40	Strongly agree
There are many ways to solve mathematics problems.	4.21	Strongly agree
The goal of mathematics is to obtain the correct answer.	4.05	Agree
It is important to know every formula to be able to solve different mathematics problems.	4.29	Strongly Agree
Mathematics have one and only answer and it can be answered in a particular or specific way.	3.86	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.21	Strongly Agree

Table 3b: Conception of students on Mathematics learning in terms of its involvement to thinking.

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Value
Mathematics is a thinking exercise just as physical exercise for the body	3.32	Moderate
Learning mathematics cannot be relied on rote memorization alone	3.72	Agree
Understanding the mathematical problem is more important than getting the correct answer.	3.78	Agree
Mathematics requires good memory and is only limited to clever ones	3.27	Moderate
Understanding the reason behind the formula is more important than simply memorizing it.	3.71	Agree
Mathematics allows students to practice their critical thinking skills	4.01	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.51	Agree

Table 3c: Conception of students on Mathematics learning in terms of its usability.

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Value
Mathematics will help me in finding a good job in the future.	3.58	Agree
Mathematics allows me to strengthen my understanding on my chosen course.	3.23	Moderate
Mathematics is a solitary activity done by individuals in isolation.	3.26	Moderate
I could use mathematics in my chosen career.	3.38	Moderate
Mathematics helps develop problem solving skills that could be used in real life situations	3.73	Agree
Mathematics is widely useful in daily life	3.90	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.43	Agree

These result is synonymous with the study presented by Sam and Ernest (2008), Loveridge (2007) and Grootenber’s stating that mathematics is identified with number, equations and formulas which involves calculations.

Further, this is in parallel to Whittin (2007) suggesting that only few students indicate that Mathematics is useful at present, most them relate usefulness in future employment.

Attitudes of Students towards Mathematics Learning

The table below presents the attitude of CHK students in terms of interest, learning preferences, confidence and understanding.

It could be surprising that the students agreed to have an interest attending Mathematics class. Although, negative attitudes have been associated with this subject, this is a good start for Mathematics educators to rebuild positive attitudes towards mathematics learning.

Furthermore, it could be noted that learners identified the importance of learning a concept to be able to understand and solve different mathematics problems. This implies that students could determine the conceptual nature of mathematics. Further, students did realize that just knowing how to calculate was not enough and understanding the concepts behind the calculation steps enabled one to be more effective in finding ways to solve problems.

It is however expected that the learners all wish that the teacher will give the formula right away to save their minds from analyzing what concept and formula are present in that scenario.

Though it's sad to note that sometimes, students don't know the reasons behind their calculations. This attitude could be attributed to the fact that students have been oriented with calculations disregarding the conceptual and theoretical framework behind those calculations.

In summary, students connect Mathematics subject between the positive and negative feelings. However, responses revealed that Math is mostly connected to negative feelings.

Responses such as "I feel confused because of the complicated problems I encounter." [r187]; "I feel like I'm going sick when learning mathematics." [r114]; "Nosebleed" [r33]; "I feel nervous, makes me crazy or irritated because it is so difficult". [r30]; "I'm having a headache in understanding math [r118] like being tortured." [r116]; "Sometimes I feel that time is so slow when math is our subject. And I'm sweating when

I can't solve the problem" [r93]; "Honestly, I am very tired of solving math problems." [r17] are being attributed when students are in a Mathematics class.

Though, it's noteworthy, however, that positive attitudes can also be seen in students as being reflected in their responses such as "I feel glad and happy in Mathematics because you can gain knowledge." [r77]; "Sometimes, Math is very interesting when I am in the mood." [r167]; "I enjoy solving math even if I answer it wrong, the most important thing is I answer it myself" [r112]; "I feel love because I want mathematics subject." [r26]; and "Math is challenging." [r185].

It can also be noted that positive attitudes could depend on the teacher as presented by two respondents: "I feel good when you understand the explanation." [r11]; and "Interesting if the topic is easy. However, if the topic is hard, I just listen to the teacher. I am happy with the different math problems however if the teacher is boring, I cannot enjoy the subject." [r4]. This implies that attitude towards a certain subject could be attributed to the teacher who have handled the said subject.

Some students also used figurative languages in describing their feelings towards mathematics subjects such as "I love math but sometimes boring although it's beautiful. It's like a girlfriend, sometimes boring, that is why you tend to look for x." [r128]; "Mathematics is like your crush, if you can't have him, just stare at him." [r100] and "I feel like I'm in the sun when solving math, it's so hot." [r114]. This signifies that deep feelings have been developed throughout their yearlong stay in the school dealing with mathematics subject.

Table 4a: Attitudes of students towards Mathematics subject with regard to interest.

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Value
I love solving mathematical problems.	3.04	Neutral
I am very interested in attending mathematics classes.	3.57	Positive
I am interested in mathematical calculations.	3.26	Neutral
I seldom try those problems no required by the teacher	3.06	Neutral
Weighted Mean	3.20	Neutral

Table 4b: Attitudes of students towards Mathematics subject with regard to preference for understanding.

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Value
Reading the explanations in the textbook is not necessary, we can learn just by reading the formulas.	3.10	Neutral
When learning a new topic, I wish that the teacher could tell us the formula right away and not ask us to look for it out for ourselves.	3.97	Positive
When learning a new topic, I wish that I could think it through by myself first and not having the teacher telling me everything.	3.17	Neutral
Understanding the content is unimportant; but it is important to know how to calculate in examinations.	3.10	Neutral
If I understand the concept concerned, I can always find a way to calculate the problems.	3.51	Positive
In learning a new topic, I am not concerned with how the formulas come about, I only care about how the formula are applied in solving problems.	3.30	Neutral
Weighted Mean	3.20	Moderate

Table 4c: Attitudes of students towards Mathematics subject with regard to confidence.

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Value
I have confidence in problems that involve substituting numbers into formulas.	3.10	Neutral

I have confidence in doing pure numerical computations.	3.25	Neutral
I have confidence in doing word problems	3.15	Neutral
Weighted Mean	2.87	Neutral

Table 4d: Attitudes of students towards Mathematics subject with regard to competence.

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Value
I fully understand the content in the mathematics class.	3.05	Neutral
Usually I fully understand word problems.	3.13	Neutral
Though I know how to calculate, sometimes I don't know the reasons for the calculation.	3.44	Positive
Weighted Mean	2.91	Neutral

These results could be further verified by the research conducted by Sam and Ernest (2008) revealing that the three most common expressions used in Mathematics are 'mathematics is difficult'; 'mathematics is boring' or 'mathematics is interesting or rewarding'.

Learning Habits towards Mathematics Learning

The table reveals that there is a considerable amount of time in which students spend in studying mathematics and doing mathematics homework. As presented in the table, students spend 34.31 percent of their time studying Mathematics and 49.13% of their time doing their homework as compared to their other subjects.

This study may imply both positive and negative. Positive in the sense that students actually preference for optional learning are quite good as being reiterated by

one student saying that “I spend more time doing math subjects so that I will understand more this subject” [r116]

Negative in such a way that students does not actually understand and have no interest with the concepts being presented in Mathematics class that’s why students spend considerable amount of time studying and doing homework like “Because I don’t have any interest in math” [r118] and “I spend more time studying mathematics because it is so difficult.” [93].

It can also be observe in the responses that students are spending such hours “So that I will not forget the given activity” [r11] to be able to “be active in math subject” [r114]. Further, they “want that my homework is correct” [r129] “to have a high grade” [r194] “to finish my studies” [r7] which limits their understanding for the said subject.

Table 5a: Number of hours spent studying and doing homework in mathematics.

	Number of Hours	Percentage
All Subjects	4.09	
Mathematics	1.40	34.31%
All Subjects Homework	1.87	
Math Homework	0.92	49.13%

The table presents the actions done by the students when meeting difficulties in learning Mathematics. It can be seen in the table that the student’s takes positive steps when encountering difficulties in understanding lesson in Mathematics

such as consulting the teacher, discussing with their classmates or searching for references to solve the given problem.

These can be found in the responses like: “I try to ask some help for those people who is good in math [r93] like my sister” r167]; “I ask my classmates or prof to know whether it’s correct and ask what’s the next step.” [r4]; and “read books [r5] and imagine [r114] and internet” [r92].

Which implies that students are actually exploring options in which they will understand different topics in Mathematics. It can also be noted that students never give-up in understanding mathematics which is a good indication that students try hard to understand topics in Math.

Table 5b: Learning habits of students when encountering difficulties in Mathematics.

Learning Habits	Mean	Description
(a)Consult the teacher	2.89	Sometimes
(b) discuss with classmates	2.91	Sometimes
(c) search for references	2.84	Sometimes

The results presented is in parallel with the research conducted by Whittin (2007) revealing that when students are having troubles in math, students depend on teachers for proper direction.

The last table presents the options being acted by the respondents when they encounter difficulties in solving mathematics problems. It can be gleaned that students learning habits sometimes explore all the options given just to solve the problem presented.

From insisting their works, consulting others to just copying other works, students do actually do things that will help them out to solve the given problem. These could be supported by the responses such as “Concentrating” [r123]; “trying hard solving math” [r194]; and by sadly sitting on my armchair and do what I can do to solve everything” [r156].

These actions could be positive in such a way that they actually find ways in solving problems and also negative, which is alarming, because they tend to copy other works because it’s the least way of having the idea that you solve the problem.

Table 5c: Learning habits of students when encountering difficulties in solving Mathematics problems.

Learning Habits	Mean	Description
(a)insist on working them out by myself	2.70	Sometimes
(b) accept other’s advise	3.18	Sometimes
(c) accept other’s assistance	3.01	Sometimes
(d) don’t mind copying others work	2.61	Sometimes

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings of the study that was conducted, conclusions and recommendations made by the researcher for the concern individuals and for further studies.

Summary of Findings

This study was conducted to determine how College of Human Kinetics (CHK) students view Mathematics learning. Thus, the following problems were sought to be answered: (1) how the CHK students do perceived the difficulty of mathematics subjects?; (2) what is the conception of CHK students towards Mathematics learning in terms of its nature as calculable; involvement to in depth thinking and usability?; (3) what is the attitudinal level CHK students towards Mathematics learning with regards to: interest, preference for understanding, confidence and competence? ; (4) what are learning habits of CHK students in Mathematics learning in terms of: number of hours spent in studying mathematics and steps in meeting difficulties in learning mathematics?

Using appropriate and valid statistical tools and measurement, results were then determined, tabulated and analyzed. It was observed that there is an almost equal ratio of males to females, having almost 43% of male population implying that there is a growing participation of males in teaching workforce.

Respondents perceived most of the mathematics subject as moderate with Advance algebra and trigonometry and college algebra perceived as difficult. However, it could be clearly observe in the responses given by the respondents that overall, they

perceived Mathematics as difficult. It could also be further observe that there is a perceived increasing difficulty of Mathematics subjects as one goes up from each year level.

Moreover, students have all agreed that mathematics is a subject of calculable, involves in depth thinking and is useful in which the first one is strongly agreed upon which means that students have been oriented with the nature of mathematics as a subject that requires calculation. It is also worthy to state that students conceived math as useful in their daily routinely activities and daily lives as a whole.

There is a moderate feeling, which is between positive and negative attitude, connected towards mathematics subject in terms of interest, preference for understanding, confidence and confidence. It is noteworthy however to say that students agreed that they have interest in attending mathematics classes which is a good start for mathematics teachers to change the climate that revolves around mathematics class.

It could also be noted that students almost spend a third to half of their hours studying or doing Mathematics homework implying a positive or a negative connotation. It maybe because of their interest in learning Mathematics more or to cope with their difficulties that they encounter learning mathematics concepts and principles.

When meeting difficulties in Mathematics learning, students sometimes take positive steps in understanding such as consulting the teacher, asking classmates or experts and searching additional references such as books. Giving up is not an option to students which a good indication of doing their best to understand Mathematics.

When meeting difficulties in solving different Mathematics problems, students sometimes do any possible options on hand to solve the latter; from insisting on doing it themselves, consulting other people to copying others work. This actions could mean both positive and negative as to options for solving to just simply copying.

Conclusion:

Based on the aforementioned results, the researcher concluded then that: students rated Mathematics as moderate or difficult with an observable increasing trend of difficulty as each student proceeds to another level; students agreed that Mathematics is a subject of calculable, involves thinking and useful, with the first conception strongly agreed by the students; students associate Mathematics with a neutral feeling as regard to interest, preference for understanding, confidence and competence; students spend a considerable time studying or doing homework in Mathematics; students sometimes take positive actions when facing difficulties in Mathematics learning; and students sometimes try any available options, even if considered as positive or negative, when meeting difficulties in solving Mathematics problems.

Recommendations:

Based on the results stated, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. Mathematics teachers must seek different strategies and methods that will help students perceived not focusing on the level of difficulty but on the immeasurable learnings one could get from learning mathematics.

2. Students should be made realized that mathematics goal is to not only developed numerical and computation skills but rather to developed lifelong skills that could be applied in real life situations.
3. Teachers must try other options that will foster positive attitudes of students towards mathematics learning such as introduction of games or other strategies that promote enjoyment and the likes.
4. Teachers must take the opportunity in giving students meaningful activities that will promote positive steps when facing difficulties in mathematics.

CHAPTER VI**BIBLIOGRAPHY**

Anna Dahlgren Johansson & Lovisa Sumpter (2010) Children's Conceptions About Mathematics And Mathematics Education Australian Journal of Educational & Developmental Psychology. Vol 7, 2007, pp 63-74

Dossey, J. (1992). The Nature of Mathematics: Its Role And Its Influence.In D. A. Grouws (Ed.), Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning (pp. 39–48). New York: Macmillan.

Fuson, K. C., Kalchman, M., & Bransford, J. D. (2005). Mathematics Understanding: An Introduction. In M. S. Donovan & J. D. Bransford (Eds), How students learn mathematics in the classroom (pp. 217–256). Washington, DC: National Academies Press.

Gavin T. L. Brown & Gerrit H. F. Hirschfeld (nd) Students' Conceptions of Assessment and Mathematics: Self-Regulation Raises Achievement1

Grootenboer, P. J. (2003). The Affective Views of Primary School Children. In N. A. Pateman, B. J. Dougherty, & J. Zillioz (Eds), Navigating between theory and practice (Proceedings of the 27th conference of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education (Vol. 3, pp. 1–8). Honolulu: University of Hawai'i.

Leveridge et al (2005). Students towards the Nature of Mathematics. Findings from the new Zealand numeracy development projects 2005.

Phyllis E. Whittin, (2007), The Mathematics Survey: A Tool For Assessing Attitudes And Disposition. The National Council of Teachers for Mathematic. Inc. www.nctm.com

Sakaadvik, Einar. M, and Richard. J (1994): “Gender Difference in Mathematics and Verbal Achievement, Self-Perception and Motivation”. British Journal of Educational Psychology,64, pp 419-428

Schoenfeld, A. H. (1992). Learning to think mathematically: Problem solving, metacognition, and sense making in mathematics. In D. A. Grouws (Ed.), Hand- book of research on mathematics teaching and learning (pp. 334–370). New York: Macmillan.

Spangler, D. A. (1992). Assessing students’ beliefs about mathematics. Arithmetic Teacher, 40(3), 148–152.

Thompson, A.G. (1992). Teachers’ Beliefs and Conceptions: A Synthesis Of The Research. In D. Grouws (Ed.), Handbook for research on mathematics teaching and learning (pp.127146). New York: Macmillan.

Wong, Lam and Wong (2001). Students’ View of Mathematics Learning: A Cross – Sectional Survey in Hong Kong.The Chinese University of Hong Kong. Education Journal (Vol 29, No. 2) winter 2001.